

ISSN 2522-3771

BM&DC Recognized

Vol. 05

Issue 01

January 2022

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An Official Publication of
MH SAMORITA HOSPITAL & MEDICAL COLLEGE, DHAKA

117 Love Road, Tejgaon, Dhaka-1208, Bangladesh

Web: www.mhsamorita.edu.bd Email: mhsamoritamcj@gmail.com

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Infant Feeding Practice among the Mothers in a Selected Area of Bangladesh

Shakil M¹, Mahejabin F², Farah S³, Ahamed MS⁴, Ali M⁵, Orin FS⁶

Abstract

Introduction: Infants are the most vulnerable group in our society. Infants constitute about 3% of the total population of Bangladesh. Child health in developing countries including Bangladesh is a matter of serious concern as the prevalence of malnutrition among children under five in Bangladesh is significantly high.

Objective: The objective of this study was to assess the patterns of infant feeding practice among the mothers having children below five years residing at Ramu upazilla, Cox's Bazar.

Materials & Methods: A descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted from March 2021 to August 2021 among the mothers having children below five years residing at Ramu upazilla, Cox's Bazar. Sample size was 440. Data were collected using a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire by face to face interview. The data were then compiled and tabulated manually according to key variables by master sheet. Then finally data were analyzed in computer using MS word and MS Excel.

Results: In this study majority of the respondents 317 (72.05%) were within the age group of 16-25 years. About 111 (25%) children were within 0-12 months of age and 232 (52.73%) were male and remaining 208 (47.27%) were female children. Among the respondents 280 (63.64%) were housewives and 141 (32.05%) were garments workers. About 419 (95%) respondents had 1-3 children and only 21 (4.77%) had 4-6 children. Among the respondents 304 (69.09%) of them took plan before conception and only 136 (30.91%) did not plan for conception. Regarding the place of child birth most of the respondents had their delivery at home (241: 54.77%). Maximum children 320 (72.73%) were cared by their mother herself and only 86 (19.54%) were cared by their grandmother/father. Majority of the children 383 (87.05%) took colostrum as their first food and most of the respondents fed colostrum to their baby (393: 89.32%). Regarding duration of exclusive breast feeding, majority of the children were only breast fed up to age of 6 months (302: 68.64%) and 164 (37.27%) children were breast fed up to age of 13-24 months. Most of the children 409 (92.95%) were vaccinated as per EPI schedule. Among them 283 (64.32%) children suffered from disease in last 3 months and 225 (79.51%) took treatment for their illness. Among them 83 (36.89%) took treatment from quack and only 76 (33.78%) children took treatment from private doctor.

Conclusion: The present study was done in selected villages of Ramu upazilla, covering a small group of population which does not represent the whole nation. Therefore, a large scale community based study is needed to know the real situation of the country.

Key Words: Infant feeding, Colostrum, Exclusive breast feeding

(MH Samorita Med Coll J 2022; 5(1): 14-20)

Introduction:

Children especially infants are at large danger of malnutrition from first six months of life when

breast milk alone is not sufficient to meet all nutritious supplies and balancing feeding needs to be in progress. Good practice of exclusive

*1. Dr. Mohammad Shakil, Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Army Medical College, Cumilla.

2. Prof. Dr. Farzana Mahejabin, Professor and Head, Department of Community Medicine, Dhaka Community Medical College

3. Dr. Shayela Farah, Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Dhaka Community Medical College

4. Dr. Md. Shakil Ahamed, MPH Student (Batch-3), Dhaka Community Medical College

5. Dr. Mumtahena Ali, MPH Student (Batch-3), Dhaka Community Medical College

6. Dr. Fatema Shahnaz Orin, MPH Student (Batch-3), Dhaka Community Medical College

* Address of correspondence: Dr. Mohammad Shakil, Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Army Medical College, Cumilla. Mobile no: 01612711572, email: mshakil1470@yahoo.com

breastfeeding can prevent 13.8% of all deaths among infants aged less than 2 years and 11.6% of under 5-years children deaths.¹ Malnutrition in all its forms, either indirectly or directly, is responsible for about half of the all deaths including infants worldwide.² Human milk is the ideal source of nutrition for infants and has numerous health benefits for the infant and the mother. Both the World Health Organization^{3,4} and the American Academy of Pediatrics⁵ recommend exclusive breast-feeding for the first 6 months of life and continued breast-feeding, with the addition of appropriate complementary foods, until 12 months and thereafter for as long as mother and baby desire. A high rate of breast-feeding is beneficial for the developing countries with regard to both economy and health. It is well known that colostrum improves the infant's chances of survival by providing both nutrition and immunization, both specific and nonspecific, during the neonatal period.⁶ Infants should be exclusively breastfed to achieve optimum growth, development and maintenance of health. Furthermore, it is safe and contains antibodies that help to protect infants and boost immunity. Consequently, optimum breastfeeding reduces the risk of diarrhea, respiratory or ear infections and other infectious diseases that increase infant mortality. Furthermore, optimal breastfeeding is also identified as a protective factor for overweight and obesity in childhood.⁷ The objective of this research work was to assess the patterns of infant feeding practice among the mothers having children below five years residing at Ramu upazilla, Cox's Bazar.

Material and Methods:

A descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted from March 2021 to August 2021 among the mothers having children below five years residing at Ramu upazilla, Cox's Bazar. Sample size was 440. Data were collected using a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire by face to face interview. The data were then compiled and tabulated manually according to key variables in master sheet. Then finally data were analyzed in computer using MS word and MS Excel.

Results:

Table -1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of the respondents (n=440)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age of children (Months)		
0-12	111	25.23
13-24	89	20.23
25-36	62	14.09
37-48	80	18.18
49-60	98	22.27
Gender of children		
Male	232	52.73
Female	208	47.27
Age of the respondents (years)		
d' 15	2	0.45
16-25	317	72.05
26-35	113	25.68
36-45	8	1.82
Religion		
Muslim	414	94.09
Hindu	26	5.91
Educational qualification		
Illiterate	48	10.91
Primary	159	36.14
Secondary	176	40
Higher Secondary	52	11.82
Others	5	1.14
Occupation		
Housewife	280	63.64
Garments worker	141	32.05
Maid	15	3.41
Day labour	4	0.90
Monthly family income (Taka)		
d' 5000	18	4.09
5001-15000	249	56.59
15001-25000	130	29.54
25001-35000	20	4.55
35001-45000	8	1.82
45001-55000	7	1.59
≥55001	8	1.82
Number of children		
1-3	419	95.23
4-6	21	4.77
Number of family members		
≤4	328	74.55
5-9	105	23.86
≥10	7	1.59

Fig-1: Distribution of the respondents by their place of child birth: (n=440).

Regarding the place of child birth, the pie chart shows that most of the respondents had their delivery at home (241; 54.77%) followed by hospital (194; 44.09%).

Fig-2: Distribution of the children by whom the child was cared (n=440)

This bar diagram shows that majority of children were cared by their mother herself (320; 72.73%) followed by their grandfather/ mother (86; 19.54%) and then by others like sister/brother (16; 3.64%).

Table 2: Distribution of the children by the pattern of first food intake by the child (n=440)

Name of the food	Frequency	%
Colostrum	383	87.05
Honey	24	5.45
Sugar mixed water	18	4.09
Water	4	0.91
Others	11	2.50
Total	440	100

Table 2 shows that majority of the children took colostrum (383; 87.05%) as their first food just after birth followed by honey (24; 5.45%) and sugar mixed water (18; 4.09%).

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by feeding of colostrum to their baby (n=440)

Feeding of colostrum	Frequency	%
Yes	393	89.32
No	47	10.68
Total	440	100

Table 3 shows that most of the respondents fed colostrum to their baby (393; 89.32%) but only (47; 10.68%) did not feed.

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by the reason for which they did not give colostrum (n=47).

Reason	Frequency	%
Colostrum is bad for newborn	2	4.26
Does not know the importance of colostrum	9	19.15
Religious taboo	2	4.26
As advised by the elders	12	25.53
Others (Inadequate breast milk, Working mother, Sickness of mother)	22	46.80
Total	47	100

Majority of the children were not given colostrum due to other causes like inadequate breast milk, working mother, sickness of mother (22; 46.80%) followed by advised by the elders (12; 25.53%). (Table-4)

Table 5: Distribution of the children by their present food habit

Name of the food	Frequency
Only breast milk	74
Artificial milk	88
Cow's milk	102
Breast milk and artificial milk	110
Breast milk and cow's milk	104
Barley or suji	130
Khichuri	227
Rice	271
Egg/Fish/Meat	261
Fruits	177
Others	11

[*Multiple response]

Regarding Children's present food habit Table 5 shows that most of the children had the habit of eating rice (271) followed by egg/fish/meat (261) and then khichuri (227).

Table 6: Distribution of the children by their duration of exclusive breast feeding (n=440).

Duration (month)	Frequency	%
≤6	302	68.64
7-12	110	25
13-24	21	4.77
≥25	7	1.59
Total	440	100

Regarding duration of exclusive breast feeding, majority of the children were only breast fed up to age of ≤6 months (302; 68.64%) followed by age of 7-12 months (110; 25%).(Table-6)

Table 7: Distribution of the respondents by up to which age they fed breast milk to their baby (n=440).

Time (month)	Frequency	%
≤6	99	22.50
7-12	86	19.55
13-24	164	37.27
25-36	82	18.63
≥37	9	2.05
Total	440	100

Table - 7 shows that majority of the children were breast fed up to age of 13-24 months (164; 37.27%) followed by age of ≤6 months (99; 22.50%) and then 7-12 months (86; 19.55%).

Table 8: Distribution of the children by their vaccination status (n=440).

Vaccination status	Frequency	%
Yes	409	92.95
No	31	7.05
Total	440	100

Table - 8 shows that most of the children were vaccinated (409; 92.95%) and only (31; 7.05%) were not.

Table 9: Distribution of the children by the cause of not giving vaccines (n=31)

Causes	Frequency	%
Don't know the immunization schedule	10	32.26
Vaccination Centre not nearby	11	35.48
Religious taboos	00	00.00
Others	10	32.26
Total	31	100.00

Table -9 shows that majority of the children were not vaccinated because the vaccination center was not nearby (11; 35.48%) followed by they didn't know the immunization schedule (10; 32.26%)

Table 10: Distribution of children by any kind of illness in last 3 months (n=440)

Any kind of illness in last 3 months	Frequency	%
Yes	283	64.32
No	157	35.68
Total	440	100.00

Majority of the children (283; 64.32%) suffered from disease in last 3 months and only (157; 35.68%) did not. (Table - 10)

Table 11: Distribution of children by taking treatment for their illness (n=283)

Taking treatment for their illness	Frequency	%
Yes	225	79.51
No	58	20.49
Total	283	100.00

Majority of the children (225; 79.51%) took treatment for their illness and only (58; 20.49%) did not. (Table 11)

Table 12: Distribution of children by the place of taking treatment (n=225)

Place of taking treatment	Frequency	%
Medical College Hospital	16	7.11
Health Centre	38	16.89
Private Doctor	76	33.78
Quack	83	36.89
Others	12	5.33
Total	225	100.00

Table - 12 shows that majority of the children took treatment from quack (83; 36.89%) then followed by private doctor (76; 33.78%)

Discussion:

Adequate nutrition during infancy and early childhood is essential to ensure the growth, health, and development of children to their full potential.⁸ The first year of an infant's life is the period of most rapid growth and an important nutrition transition, when infants are given various types of complementary foods along with breast milk. The present study was done with a view to detect the breastfeeding practices & awareness regarding usefulness of it among the mothers of a selected village in Ramu, Cox's Bazar in Bangladesh. The majority of the respondents (72.05%) were in 16-25 age groups. Most of the respondents in our study were Muslim (94.09%) followed by Hindu (5.91%). As per Bangladesh bureau of statistics majority of the people of Bangladesh are Muslim (89.35%). In our study 40% respondents had completed their secondary level of education followed by 36.14% had completed their primary level of education and 10.91% were found illiterate. Another study shows that, mothers in the rural and urban region of Bangladesh 15% were illiterate, 44% were primary passed, 29% secondary passed, 10% were under graduate and 2% were above graduate respectively.⁹ In this study most of the respondents (63.64%) were housewives followed by garments worker (32.05%) and 4.31% respondents were engaged with other occupation. The maximum monthly income of family was Tk 100000 whereas majority of the respondents (56.59%) had monthly family income ranging from Tk 5001-15000 followed by Tk 15001-25000 (29.54%). In south west region of Bangladesh, 60% of pregnant women had family income Tk <5000, 20% had family income in Tk 5000-8000 range and 13.25% had family income in Tk 8000-10000 range while only 6% had family income Tk >10000, which differs from our study. Our study showed almost all the respondents (95%) had 1-3 children and remaining had 4-6 children. Average number of family member was 4 but as per Bangladesh bureau of statistics, population and housing census 2011, average family size in rural Bangladesh was 4.35.¹⁰ Regarding the place of child birth, most of the respondents had their delivery at home (54.77%) followed by hospital (44.09%) and majority of children were cared by their mother

herself (72.73%). The majority of births in rural Bangladesh are carried out in unhygienic conditions by relatives and traditional birth attendants (TBAs). High incidence of maternal and infant mortality of Bangladesh that could be reduced if childbirth took place in health centers or under the supervision of trained TBAs.¹¹ As per EPI fact sheet 2013, only 31% delivery was conducted by skilled birth attendance.¹² We found that majority of the children took colostrum (383; 87.05%) as their first food just after birth followed by honey (24; 5.45%) and sugar mixed water (18; 4.09%). A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted by Khatun M et al¹³ among mothers with infant of high socioeconomic group, the residents of Sobhanbag government colony & Panthopath Green road residential area and low socioeconomic group slum area of Rayer bazar, Dhaka from October 2007 to May 2008 and they found Breast milk as the first food to their babies was given by 71.2% mothers of high & 65.4% of low socioeconomic group. Our study showed that most of the respondents fed colostrum to their baby (393; 89.32%) but only (47; 10.68%) did not feed. Similar was found among Garo mothers done by Uddin MB¹⁴ in Netrokona District Bangladesh and found 80% of Garo mothers and 89.4% of Non Garo mothers gave colostrums to their babies. Zewde GT¹⁵ found overall good attitude towards colostrum feeding among postnatal mothers was 89% (271) in Ethiopia. The overall prevalence of good practice of colostrum feeding among lactating women was 56.2% in Ethiopia study done by Tadesse M¹⁶. A cross sectional observational study done by Islam MS¹⁷ among mothers having child aged between 0-6 months of age in rural area of Bangladesh and found majority (63%) of the mothers had given colostrum to their child. Wassie AY¹⁸ found positive attitude 239 (69.9%) towards colostrum feeding among mothers having child aged between 0-6 months of age in a rural Nawabgonj Upazila, Dhaka district. Regarding duration of exclusive breast feeding, majority of the children were only breast fed up to age of ≤6 months (302; 68.64%) followed by age of 7-12 months (110; 25%). A cross-sectional study done by Sultana M et al¹⁹ included 397 mothers having infants aged 0-6 months who sought care at Noakhali Sadar Upazila, Noakhali, Bangladesh. They found the mothers had an overall favorable attitude towards exclusive breastfeeding; however, 38.3% of mothers did not exclusively breastfeed their children. In Syrian

refugees in Lebanon a study done by Daher S²⁰ among the mothers of children (6-24 months) showed that EBF for four (49.6%), and six (36%) months. Iqbal A²¹ conducted a study among women of reproductive age (15-49 years), working in Readymade Garment sector, with children aged 6-23 months in Dhaka, Bangladesh found majority knew about exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) (76%), duration to continue breastfeeding (73%). Regarding up to which age they fed breast milk to their baby, we found majority of the children were breast fed up to age of 13-24 months (164; 37.27%) followed by age of 56 months (99; 22.50%) and then 7-12 months (86; 19.55%). A study conducted by Sharmin A et al²² at Ad-din shisu Hospital in Jashore, Bangladesh during a period of 5 months starting from July 2018 to November 2018, they found around 46.9% mothers practiced early initiation of breastfeeding and they offered breast milk to their newborn right away (within one hour) after delivery. A systematic review of peer-reviewed literature was performed by Dukuzumuremyi JPC et al²³ and found that mothers had practiced exclusive breastfeeding for at least six months. Karim M et al²⁴ found out of 320 respondents about 137(42.8%) of the responding mothers continued breast feeding to their babies for 9-12 months among the villagers of selected villages at Dhamrai upazilla health complex in 2011. Our study showed almost all the children were vaccinated (92.95%) and majority of them completed their vaccination schedule (69.19%). As per EPI fact sheet Bangladesh 2013 out of 64 districts, all districts had >80% coverage for DPT-Hib-HepB3 and 33 (52%) districts had > 90% coverage for MCV1 (measles containing vaccine 1st dose).²⁵ The reasons for not giving vaccines are vaccination centers were not nearby (48%) and didn't know the immunization schedule (32.26%). About 64% children suffered from disease in last three months, among them 79% children got treatment for their illness but majority of their guardian took treatment from quack.

Conclusion:

This cross sectional study describes infant feeding practice among the mothers in a selected area in Bangladesh. In this study we also observed that colostrum was the first food given to the children just after birth. Regarding immunization, introduction of vaccination was good. In case of few children, there was incomplete vaccination which is

a great concern regarding the health of the children. The present food habit of the children in the study area was comparatively well. Most of the children were suffering from different kinds of illness such as fever, common cold, flue etc. and most of the mothers sought treatment from private & non registered doctors. According to the findings of this study the children in this semi urban area were deprived from cleanliness, immunization and proper treatment due to their ignorance, lack of education, religious taboos and socio-economic barriers

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